

Code Structure

Qualitative Analysis BOR project

02/12/2024 11:24

Hierarchical Name	Nickname	Aggregate	User Assigned Color
Code			
Codes			
Codes\Accountability		No	None
Codes\AI		No	None
Codes\Assessment		No	None
Codes\Bias (data, model...)		No	None
Codes\Collaboration		No	None
Codes\Data		Yes	None
Codes\Data\Data challenges		No	None
Codes\Data\Data integrity		No	None
Codes\Data\Data quality		No	None
Codes\Data\Sensitive personal data		No	None
Codes\EDI - Equality, Diveristy and Inclusion		No	None
Codes\Ethics		No	None
Codes\Excellence		No	None
Codes\Expectations		Yes	None
Codes\Expectations\Expectations met		No	None
Codes\Expectations\Information security		No	None
Codes\Expectations\Metrics		No	None
Codes\Expectations\Morality		No	None
Codes\Expectations\More focused sessions or discussion		No	None
Codes\Expectations\Patient and Public involvement		No	None
Codes\Expectations\Solutions		No	None
Codes\Expectations\What is already in place		No	None
Codes\FAIR principles		Yes	None
Codes\FAIR principles\Accessibility		No	None
Codes\FAIR principles\Findability		No	None
Codes\FAIR principles\Interoperability		No	None
Codes\FAIR principles\Reusability		No	None
Codes\Open Research		Yes	None
Codes\Open Research\Obstacles to Open Research		No	None
Codes\Open Research\Openness		Yes	None
Codes\Open Research\Openness\Open access		No	None
Codes\Open Research\Openness\Open code		No	None

Hierarchical Name	Nickname	Aggregate	User Assigned Color
Codes\\Open Research\\Openness\\Open data		No	None
Codes\\Peer-review		No	None
Codes\\Practical recommendations		Yes	None
Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Awareness of what is going on		No	None
Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Beyond Imperial		No	None
Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Develop policies		No	None
Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Enhance practices		No	None
Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Incentives and recognition		No	None
Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Public involvement		No	None
Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Standards		No	None
Codes\\Practical recommendations\\Take action from general to specific		No	None
Codes\\Practices and behaviours to improve research quality		No	None
Codes\\Reliability		No	None
Codes\\Research culture		No	None
Codes\\Sustainability		No	None
Codes\\Transparency		No	None
Codes\\Trustworthiness		No	None